

1 **BRAF V600E activates Akt3.**

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8 We demonstrate here that expression of the oncogenic Raf mutant BRAF V600E results in activation of Akt3.

9 Citations

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11 2. Testa, J.R. and Bellacosa, A., 2001. AKT plays a central role in tumorigenesis. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 98(20), pp.10983-10985.